

Association Between Gender, M. Alvarado Scoring System, Tzanaki's Scoring System with Status of HPR in Acute Appendicitis PatientsVasantani Manish Laxmandas¹, Arun Kumar S², Sunil Subhash Joshi³, Karthik N⁴¹Senior Resident, Department of General Surgery, GMERS Medical College Godhra, Panchmahal Gujarat-389001, India²Assistant Professor, Department of General Surgery, Chikkaballapur Institute of Medical Sciences, Chikkaballapura³Professor and HOD Surgery, Chikkaballapura Institute of Medical Sciences, Chikkaballapura⁴Assistant Professor, General Surgery, CIMS, KMC

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Abstract:

Background: The abdomen is commonly compared to a Pandora's Box, and for a good reason. Since the abdomen contains within it innumerable viscera and other anatomical components, the diseases of the abdomen give rise to a lot of clinical curiosity. A meticulous examination of the abdomen and clinical correlation is one of the most important diagnostic tools and becomes cornerstone of management in many conditions presenting with abdominal pain.

Objective: To study the Association between Gender, M. Alvarado Scoring System, and Tzanaki's Scoring System with Status of HPR in Acute Appendicitis Patients

Methods: An Observational study was conducted in our institute in 100 patients with the clinical diagnosis of AA undergoing emergency appendectomy over a period of 1 year 4 months. The MASS & Tzanaki's score was obtained at the time of admission and the histopathological diagnosis of AA was considered as final diagnosis.

Result: There is a Male predominance with a ratio of 1.8:1. There is a higher prevalence of AA in second decade (62%). RLQ Pain (100%) and Nausea/Vomiting (98%) were the consistent symptoms. The negative Appendectomy rate is 6%.

Conclusion: This study shows that Tzanaki's scoring system can be used as an effective modality in the establishment of accuracy in diagnosis of acute appendicitis.

Keywords: Gender, M. Alvarado Scoring System, Tzanaki's Scoring System, Status of HPR, Appendicitis Patients.

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Introduction

Appendicitis is the inflammation of the appendix. It is a disease of the young, with 40% of cases occurring between the ages of 10 and 29 years. [1,2] Acute appendicitis (AA) is one of the most common surgical emergencies in the world, with 7–12% of the general population being affected. [3] Acute appendicitis is one of the commonest causes for acute abdomen in any general surgical practice. [4] From the time that it was first described by Reginald Heber Fitz in 1886, [5] it has remained a topic of serial research works for various factors ranging from its aetiology, to its management options.

The cornerstone of the diagnosis of AA has traditionally been the combination of history and physical examination. However, at times, the clinical evaluation of patients with suspected AA become complex. Prompt and accurate diagnosis is impera-

tive to decrease the frequency of complications, such as appendicular perforation, appendicular abscess and Phlegmon formation which are associated with increase morbidity and mortality. Complications are more common in extreme age group of patients who have greater perforation rate with more chances of Intra Peritoneal spread of infection due to their poor localizing capability. [6,7]

Acute Appendicitis is one of the most common causes of abdominal surgical emergencies with lifetime prevalence of approximately 1 in 7 worldwide. [8] It is associated with high morbidity and occasional mortality related to failure of making an early diagnosis. Acute appendicitis mimics many other intra-abdominal conditions due to which the surgeon faces dilemma in arriving at a confident preoperative diagnosis, delayed diagnosis can lead to complications, due to which there are various

scoring systems including different parameters were introduced, which supplements the clinical judgment in improving the diagnostic accuracy. A high rate of Negative Appendectomy of 15%-20% has been accepted in the past at the cost of preventing complications. Though mortality of negative appendectomy was less associated with morbidities like Surgical Site Infections, Faecal Fistula, Adhesions, Future Hernias. For these reasons Negative Appendectomy should be minimized by improving the diagnostic accuracy.

Diagnosis of acute appendicitis is primarily based on clinical impression, various laboratory parameters of Inflammation (Leucocytosis and Raised C reactive protein), radiological tools like USG or CT and laparoscopy. This armamentarium has definitely increased the diagnostic accuracy and help to reduce negative appendectomy rate. However, these techniques are not available universally.

Material and Methods

This Observational study was conducted Among Participants are those patients presenting to Department of General Surgery, District Hospital, Dharwad between January 2021 to April 2022 with suspected clinically as AA and underwent surgery for the same were included in the study with ≥ 18 years of age fulfilling Inclusion criteria and Exclusion criteria between January 2021 to April 2022.

The Modified Alvarado score and Tzanaki's score were calculated from the collected data. Histology results from the removed appendices were followed up. The negative appendectomy rate was then calculated. Prior to start of the study institutional ethical committee approval was taken.

Patients admitted as IN PATIENT at Department of General Surgery, District Hospital, Dharwad between January 2021 to April 2022 with suspected clinically as AA and underwent surgery for the same were included in the study

Sample Size: A sample size of 100 Patients fulfilling inclusion and exclusion criteria undergoing Open/Lap appendectomy in Department of General Surgery, District Hospital, Dharwad.

Inclusion Criteria

- Age ≥ 18 years of age
- Participants with clinical diagnosis of Acute Appendicitis
- Patients undergoing Open as well as Lap Appendectomy
- Patient with scores below the cut off values (for MASS and Tzanaki's score) based on Clinical Assessment and Judgment
- Patient willing to participate and give consent for the study

Exclusion Criteria:

- Age < 18 years of age

- Patient with alternative diagnosis during surgery with or without an inflamed appendix
- Patients with Appendicular Mass, Appendicular Abscess, Appendicular Perforation, Generalized Peritonitis
- Patient not willing to participate and did not give consent for the study
- Patient with blunt trauma abdomen
- Patient with recurrent appendicitis
- Patient not fit for surgery
- Patient with right lower abdomen pathology other than appendix

Methods

- This Observational Hospital based Cross-sectional study includes 100 patients ≥ 18 years of age, admitted in the Department of General Surgery, District Hospital, Dharwad during the period of January 2021 to April 2022 with clinical suspicion of acute appendicitis and underwent Open/Lap appendectomy
- After approval by local bioethics committees, informed consent was obtained
- All cases had undergone thorough history and detailed clinical examination at the time of admission as part of routine management.
- Total and differential leucocyte count was measured using an auto-analyzer
- As USG is technician dependent, only those patients who underwent abdominal USG by Consultant Radiologist were included in the study to exclude observer bias.
- He is blinded to the results of physical examination and blood report of the patients.
- Well established ultrasonographic criteria were applied to discriminate an acutely inflamed appendix from a normal one.
- Both Modified Alvarado Score and Tzanaki's score are done for all the patients at the time of admission and prior to surgery
- Even the patients with scores below the cut off values were subjected to surgery based on clinical assessment and judgment.
- Patients were either subjected to emergency laparotomy/ Open or Lap appendectomy at the time of admission or after few hours of conservative management.
- Emergency appendectomy was done by Open/Lap method under spinal or general anaesthesia in all cases
- Final diagnosis to be confirmed by Histopathological Examination of the specimen by the pathologist.
- Data was analysed to compare the efficacy of both scoring systems in diagnosing Acute appendicitis.

Sonographic Criteria's for Appendicitis

- Noncompressible appendix of size > 6 mm AP diameter,
- Hyperechoic thickened appendix wall > 2

mm—target sign.

- Presence of Appendicolith.
- Interruption of submucosal continuity.
- Peri-appendicular fluid.

Data Collection Technique and Tools

- Every Patient Included in This Study Will Be Counselling and Consent Taken.
- Detailed History Taking, Clinical Examination Will Be Done to Satisfy Inclusion and Exclusion Criteria.
- Patients Will Be Scored According to Modified Alvarado Score as Well as Tzanaki's Score at The Time of Admission and Prior to Surgery.
- USG will be Done Using 5 mhz Linear Transducer.
- Total and differential leucocyte count was measured using an auto-analyzer
- The Final Diagnosis Will Be Confirmed by Histopathological Examination of The Specimen by Pathologist.
- After Thorough Clinical Examination, Radiological Examination and Laboratory Investigations Modified Alvarado Score and Tzanaki's Score Will Be Calculated.

Modified Alvarado Score:

Total Score: 9

Patient with Score 6 or >6 Will Undergo Appendectomy and Histopathology Results Will Be

Analysed.

Tzanaki's Score:

Total Score: 15

Patient with Score >8 Will Undergo Appendectomy and Histopathology Sample Will Be Analysed.

Data Analysis

- Patients Data were collected.
- After collection of Data, entire data will be statistically analysed using Statistical Package for Social Sciences (SPSS Ver 22.0, IBM Corporation; NY, USA) for MS Windows with Descriptive statistics including Frequency, Percentage, Mean and Standard Deviation.
- The agreement between MAS and Tzanaki's scoring system was calculated by using Kappa statistics.
- Sensitivity, Specificity, PPV, NPV, Accuracy and other related findings were calculated.
- P-values less than 0.05 will be considered to be statistically significant. (5% level of Statistical significance)

Results

Of the 100 patients studied, 22% were below 20 years of age, 62% were between the age of 21-30 years, 11% were between the age of 31-40 years and 5% were above the age of 40. The mean age of patients was 25.69 years with a standard deviation of 7.58 years

Table 1: Age wise distribution of patients

Age groups	No of patients	% of patients
<=20yrs	22	22.00
21-30yrs	62	62.00
31-40yrs	11	11.00
>=41yrs	5	5.00
Total	100	100.00
Mean age	25.69	
SD age	7.58	

Of the 100 patients studied, 64% were male and 36% were female.

Table 2: Gender wise distribution of patients

Gender	No of patients	% Of patients
Male	64	64.00
Female	36	36.00
Total	100	100.00

Table 3: Gender and age wise distribution of patients

Age groups	Male	%	Female	%	Total	%
<=20yrs	14	21.88	8	22.22	22	22.00
21-30yrs	42	65.63	20	55.56	62	62.00
31-40yrs	5	7.81	6	16.67	11	11.00
>=41yrs	3	4.69	2	5.56	5	5.00
Total	64	100.00	36	100.00	100	100.00
Mean age	25.17		26.61		25.69	
SD age	7.18		8.28		7.58	

Of the 100 patients studied, 64% were male, amongst which 65.63% male patients were between the age of 21-30 years and only 4.69% of male patients were above the age of 40 years whereas 36% were female, amongst

which 55.56% female patients were between the age of 21-30 years and only 5.56% of female patients were above the age of 40 years. The mean age of male patients was 25.17 years with a standard deviation of 7.18 years. And the mean age of female patients was 26.61 years with a standard deviation of 8.28 years.

Table 4: Association between gender and M. Alvarado Score

M. Alvarado score	Male	%	Female	%	Total	%
<6	37	57.81	17	47.22	54	54.00
>=6	27	42.19	19	52.78	46	46.00
Total	64	100.00	36	100.00	100	100.00

Chi-square=1.1040, p=0.3080

Of the 100 patients studied, 54% (n = 54) patients were having M. Alvarado score below 6, amongst them, 57.81% were male patients and 47.22% were female patients. 46% (n = 46) patients were having M. Alvarado score 6 or above 6, amongst them, 42.19% were male patients and 52.78% were female patients.

Table 5: Association between gender And Tzanaki's Score

TZANAKIS score	Male	%	Female	%	Total	%
<=8	10	15.63	8	22.22	18	18.00
>8	54	84.38	28	77.78	82	82.00
Total	64	100.00	36	100.00	100	100.00

Chi-square=0.6790, p=0.4100

Of the 100 patients studied, 18 (18%) patients were having Tzanaki's score 8 or below 8, amongst them, 10 were male patients and 8 were female patients. 82 (82%) patients were having Tzanaki's score above 8, amongst them, 54 were male patients and 28 were female patients.

Table 6: Association between gender and Status of HPR

HPR	Male	%	Female	%	Total	%
Negative	3	4.69	3	8.33	6	6.00
Positive	61	95.31	33	91.67	94	94.00
Total	64	100.00	36	100.00	100	100.00

Chi-square=0.5430, p=0.4610

Of the 100 patients studied, 6% (n= 6) patients were found to be negative for HPR and 94% (n= 94) patients were found to be positive for HPR amongst which 3 were male and 3 were female.

Table 7: Comparison of Male and Females with M. Alvarado Score and Tzanaki's Scores By Independent T Test

Gender	M. Alvarado score		TZANAKIS scores	
	Mean	SD	Mean	SD
Male	5.02	1.80	10.78	3.38
Female	5.47	2.02	10.53	3.75
Total	5.18	1.89	10.69	3.50
t-value	-1.1631		0.3457	
p-value	0.2476		0.7303	

Of the 100 patients studied, mean value for male patients in M. Alvarado score was 5.02 whereas, mean value for male patients in Tzanaki's score was 10.78 and mean value for female patients in M. Alvarado score was 5.47 whereas, mean value for female patients in Tzanaki's score was 10.53.

Discussion

Analyzing both Tzanaki's scoring system and MASS, it was found that both Tzanaki's and

MASS were easy to perform as they mainly relied upon clinical symptoms and signs, along with basic laboratory investigations with Tzanaki's depending on radiological investigation i.e., USG as well. The times taken to apply the scores (both Tzanaki's and MASS) were minimal, and did not cause any undue delay in management. Even though MASS is a routinely used scoring system for the diagnosis of acute appendicitis worldwide, it has found to be lacking in its sensitivity and specificity.

Table 8: Comparison of gender wise distribution of patients of the present study with other studies

Study	Male: Female
Malik A. A. et al [9]	1.2: 1
S. Dharmarajan et al [10]	1.5: 1
Shahid-ul-haq Dar et al [11]	1.6: 1
Present study	1.8: 1

In this table, present study is closely related to the Shahid-ul-haq Dar et al study & Faris Muhammed Mahmood, et al study.

Table 9: Comparison of age wise distribution of patients of the present study with other studies

Study	Mean Age (Years)
Malik A. A. et al [9]	24.21
S. Dharmarajan et al [10]	22.93
Shahid-ul-haq Dar et al [11]	25
Present study	25.69

In this table, present study is closely related to the Malik A. A. et al study & Shahid-ul-haq Dar et al study. Present study is closely related to the Shahid-ul-haq Dar et al study regarding most common symptom of patients.

Conclusion

Acute appendicitis is a common surgical emergency. Good clinical judgment aided by investigation scoring system can help to reduce the negative appendectomy rate. Ultrasound scan has now become easily available, even in developing countries and it can immensely aid the surgeon in diagnosis. Though acute appendicitis is a clinical diagnosis, the Tzanaki's scoring system can complement the clinical diagnosis with the help of USG (Non-Invasive).

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